

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for DDX1 (UniProt ID: Q92499) for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence

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Abstract

The DEAD-box helicase 1, DDX1, plays a role in fundamental processes like RNA translation, splicing, and processing. To facilitate further cellular investigations of DDX1, we have characterized eleven DDX1 commercial antibodies for western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While the use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

Q92499, *DDX1*, DDX1, DEAD-box helicase 1, DEAD box protein 1, ATP-dependent RNA helicase DDX1, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

The DEAD box family of proteins are putative RNA helicases that contain a characteristic ATP hydrolysis motif named DEAD “Asp-Glu-Ala-Asp” (1). DDX1 acts to unwind double-stranded RNA for other processing factors to access the pre-messenger RNA (mRNA) 3' cleavage site (2), and activates mRNA translation in consortium with other proteins of the machinery (3). Moreover, DDX1 participates in transfer RNA splicing (4), and ribosomal RNA processing (5). In addition to its role in repairing double-strand breaks in DNA (6), DDX1 is also required for maintaining cytoplasmic mRNA levels to protect cells exposed to oxidative stress (7). Due to its implication in various types of cancers (8-10) and vital functions related to its helicase activity, DDX1 remains extensively studied at the molecular level. Lastly, *DDX1* was identified as a novel gene associated with Alzheimer's disease (11, 12).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (13). It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available antibodies against the corresponding protein (13). Here we characterized eleven commercial DDX1 antibodies, selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturers, for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of DDX1 properties and function.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (14) and in Table 3 of this data note (13).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cells (15, 16). The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million “TPM” + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (17). The U2OS expresses the *DDX1* transcript at $6.6 \log_2$ TPM+1. A *DDX1* KO U2OS cell line was obtained from Abcam (Table 1).

To screen all eleven antibodies by western blot, WT and *DDX1* KO protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with DDX1 antibodies in parallel (Figure 1).

We then assessed the capability of all eleven antibodies to capture DDX1 from U2OS protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. For the immunoblot step, a specific DDX1 antibody identified previously (refer to Figure 1) was selected. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 2).

For immunofluorescence, the eleven antibodies were screened using a mosaic strategy. First, U2OS WT and *DDX1* KO cells were labelled with different fluorescent dyes in order to distinguish the two cell lines, and the DDX1 antibodies were evaluated. Both WT and KO lines imaged in the same field of view to reduce staining, imaging and image analysis bias (Figure 3). Quantification of immunofluorescence intensity in hundreds of WT and KO cells was performed for each antibody tested, and the images presented in Figure 3 are representative of this analysis (13).

In conclusion, we have screened eleven DDX1 commercial antibodies by western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human U2OS WT and *DDX1* KO cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 3 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all three applications (17). Several high-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect DDX1 were identified in all applications. Researchers who wish to study DDX1 in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available DDX1 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in DDX1, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. DDX1 experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) (13). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

Cell lines used and primary antibodies tested in this study are listed in Table 1 and 2, respectively. To ensure that the cell lines and antibodies are cited properly and can be easily identified, we have included their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers, or RRID (18, 19). U2OS KO clone corresponding to the *DDX1* gene was generated with low passage cells at Abcam. Two guide RNAs were used to induce a 62bp deletion in Exon 13 of the *DDX1* gene (sequence guide 1: TATTCCCTAAGGTAATGCAC, sequence guide 2: TGTTTCAGCTAACTCCCGGGA).

Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse antibodies are (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520). Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse secondary antibodies (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A-21429 and A-21424).

Antibody screening by western blot

U2OS WT and *DDX1* KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000 x *g* for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) Or Clarity Western ECL Substrate

(Bio-Rad, cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg of antibody to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

U2OS WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 x g for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~18 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

U2OS WT and *DDX1* KO cells were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number C2925 and C34565). The nuclei were labelled with DAPI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. Number D3571) fluorescent stain. WT and KO cells were plated on a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator at 37°C, 5% CO₂. Cells were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) (VWR, cat. number 100503-917) in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Wisent, cat. number 311-010-CL). Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP151-500) for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum (Gibco, cat. number 16210-064) and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary DDX1 antibodies overnight at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 µg/ml for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.95 water immersion objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using

CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification (20). Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: - Abcam-ABCD antibodies- ABclonal- Aviva Systems Biology -Bio Techne -Cell Signalling Technology -Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank -GeneTex – Horizon Discovery – Proteintech – Synaptic Systems –Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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References

1. Linder P, Jankowsky E. From unwinding to clamping - the DEAD box RNA helicase family. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol.* 2011;12(8):505-16.
2. Bleoo S, Sun X, Hendzel MJ, Rowe JM, Packer M, Godbout R. Association of human DEAD box protein DDX1 with a cleavage stimulation factor involved in 3'-end processing of pre-mRNA. *Mol Biol Cell.* 2001;12(10):3046-59.
3. Pazo A, Perez-Gonzalez A, Oliveros JC, Huarte M, Chavez JP, Nieto A. hCLE/RTRAF-HSPC117-DDX1-FAM98B: A New Cap-Binding Complex That Activates mRNA Translation. *Front Physiol.* 2019;10:92.
4. Popow J, Jurkin J, Schleiffer A, Martinez J. Analysis of orthologous groups reveals archease and DDX1 as tRNA splicing factors. *Nature.* 2014;511(7507):104-7.
5. Suzuki T, Katada E, Mizuoka Y, Takagi S, Kazuki Y, Oshimura M, et al. A novel all-in-one conditional knockout system uncovered an essential role of DDX1 in ribosomal RNA processing. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2021;49(7):e40.
6. Li L, Germain DR, Poon HY, Hildebrandt MR, Monckton EA, McDonald D, et al. DEAD Box 1 Facilitates Removal of RNA and Homologous Recombination at DNA Double-Strand Breaks. *Mol Cell Biol.* 2016;36(22):2794-810.
7. Li L, Garg M, Wang Y, Wang W, Godbout R. DEAD box 1 (DDX1) protein binds to and protects cytoplasmic stress response mRNAs in cells exposed to oxidative stress. *J Biol Chem.* 2022;298(8):102180.
8. Godbout R, Li L, Liu RZ, Roy K. Role of DEAD box 1 in retinoblastoma and neuroblastoma. *Future Oncol.* 2007;3(5):575-87.
9. Tanaka K, Ikeda N, Miyashita K, Nuriya H, Hara T. DEAD box protein DDX1 promotes colorectal tumorigenesis through transcriptional activation of the LGR5 gene. *Cancer Sci.* 2018;109(8):2479-89.
10. Germain DR, Graham K, Glubrecht DD, Hugh JC, Mackey JR, Godbout R. DEAD box 1: a novel and independent prognostic marker for early recurrence in breast cancer. *Breast Cancer Res Treat.* 2011;127(1):53-63.
11. Axtman AD, Brennan PE, Frappier-Brinton T, Betarbet R, Carter GW, Fu H, et al. Open drug discovery in Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimers Dement (N Y).* 2023;9(2):e12394.
12. Zhang YR, Wu BS, Chen SD, Yang L, Deng YT, Guo Y, et al. Whole exome sequencing analyses identified novel genes for Alzheimer's disease and related dementia. *Alzheimers Dement.* 2024;20(10):7062-78.
13. Ayoubi R, Ryan J, Gonzalez Bolivar S, Alende C, Ruiz Moleon V, Fotouhi M, et al. A consensus platform for antibody characterization. *Nat Protoc.* 2024.
14. Biddle MS, Virk HS. YCharOS open antibody characterisation data: Lessons learned and progress made F1000Research 2023. 2023;12:1344.
15. Laflamme C, McKeever PM, Kumar R, Schwartz J, Kolaoudouzan M, Chen CX, et al. Implementation of an antibody characterization procedure and application to the major ALS/FTD disease gene C9ORF72. *Elife.* 2019;8.
16. Alshafie W, Fotouhi M, Shlaifer I, Ayoubi R, Edwards AM, Durcan TM, et al. Identification of highly specific antibodies for Serine/threonine-protein kinase TBK1 for use in immunoblot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. *F1000Res.* 2022;11:977.
17. Ayoubi R, Ryan J, Biddle MS, Alshafie W, Fotouhi M, Bolivar SG, et al. Scaling of an antibody validation procedure enables quantification of antibody performance in major research applications. *Elife.* 2023;12.
18. Bandrowski A, Pairish M, Eckmann P, Grethe J, Martone ME. The Antibody Registry: ten years of registering antibodies. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2023;51(D1):D358-d67.
19. Bairoch A. The Cellosaurus, a Cell-Line Knowledge Resource. *J Biomol Tech.* 2018;29(2):25-38.
20. Stringer C, Wang T, Michaelos M, Pachitariu M. Cellpose: a generalist algorithm for cellular segmentation. *Nat Methods.* 2021;18(1):100-6.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Abcam	ab263976	CVCL_0042	U2OS	WT
Abcam	ab323670	CVCL_E7RY	U2OS	<i>DDX1</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the DDX1 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
ABclonal	A6575	0022330101	AB_2767169	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.33	Wb, IP, IF
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP36379	QC11282-90324	AB_2045573	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP74479	QC44877-41773	AB_3073943	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	MAB9615**	CKZZ0122061	AB_3075536	recombinant mono	2220A	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP2-61745*	160325	AB_3076152	monoclonal	3E5E2	mouse	1.00	Wb, IP, IF
GeneTex	GTX105205	39904	AB_2036748	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.76	Wb, IF
GeneTex	GTX107931	39932	AB_2036749	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.13	Wb
Proteintech	11357-1-AP	45484	AB_2092222	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.75	Wb, IP, IF
Proteintech	67991-1-Ig*	10022866	AB_2918740	monoclonal	1G10G4	mouse	1.00	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	703141**	2079654	AB_2784565	recombinant mono	13H24L5	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-31711*	YJ4089451A	AB_2787335	monoclonal	3E5B2	mouse	1.00	Wb, IF

Wb=western blot; IP=immunoprecipitation; IF= immunofluorescence, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody

Table 3: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

Western blot			Immunoprecipitation			Immunofluorescence		
Successful antibody	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody	Successful antibody	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody	WT/KO cell mosaic	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody
WT KO	WT KO	WT KO	SM UB IP	SM UB IP	SM UB IP	WT	WT	WT
WT	WT	WT	SM	SM	SM	KO	KO	KO
KO	KO	KO	UB	UB	UB	WT	WT	WT
IP	IP	IP	IP	IP	IP	KO	KO	KO
kDa	kDa	kDa	kDa	kDa	kDa			
245-	245-	245-	245-	245-	245-			
135-	135-	135-	135-	135-	135-			
75-	75-	75-	75-	75-	75-			
48-	48-	48-	48-	48-	48-			
25-	25-	25-	25-	25-	25-			
11-	11-	11-	11-	11-	11-			
Target protein detected (arrowhead)	Target protein detected (arrowhead) among others	Target protein not detected	Target protein captured in the IP	Target protein captured in the IP	Target protein not captured in the IP	Target protein detected (white staining)	Target protein not detected	

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Figure 1: DDX1 antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: DDX1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 3: DDX1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: DDX1 antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of U2OS WT and *DDX1* KO were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated DDX1 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: A6575 at 1/1000, ARP36379 at 1/1000, ARP74479 at 1/1000, MAB9615** at 1/1000, NBP2-61745* at 1/500, GTX105205 at 1/1000, GTX107931 at 1/1000, 11357-1-AP at 1/2000, 67991-1-Ig* at 1/5000, 703141** at 1/5000, MA5-31711* at 1/500. Predicted band size: 82.4 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: DDX1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

U2OS lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed overnight using 1 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated DDX1 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the DDX1 antibody 703141** which was used at 1/1000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate; n/s= non-specific signal. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 3: DDX1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

U2OS WT and *DDX1* KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio on coverslips. Cells were stained with the indicated DDX1 antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (WT), red (antibody staining) and far-red (KO) channels was performed. Representative images of the merged blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. When an antibody was recommended for immunofluorescence by the supplier, we tested it at the recommended dilution. The rest of the antibodies were tested at 1 and 2 µg/ml, and the final concentration was selected based on the detection range of the microscope used and a quantitative analysis not shown here. Antibody dilutions used: A6575 at 1/1000, ARP36379 at 1/500, ARP74479 at 1/500, MAB9615** at 1/500, NBP2-61745* at 1/1000, GTX105205 at 1/800, GTX107931 at 1/150, 11357-1-AP at 1/800, 67991-1-Ig* at 1/1000, 703141** at 1/500, MA5-31711* at 1/1000. Bars = 10 µm. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.